

Table 1. Rate constants for the oxidation of cinnamic acid by PCC at 298 K

10^3 [PCC] (mol dm ⁻³)	[CiA] (mol dm ⁻³)	[TsOH] (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s ⁻¹)
1.00	0.10	0.00	14.1
1.00	0.20	0.00	27.2
1.00	0.40	0.00	55.1
1.00	0.60	0.00	82.2
1.00	0.80	0.00	110
1.00	1.00	0.00	135
2.00	0.20	0.00	28.4
4.00	0.20	0.00	26.6
6.00	0.20	0.00	27.0
8.00	0.20	0.00	27.7
1.00	0.10	0.10	18.8
1.00	0.10	0.20	23.7
1.00	0.10	0.40	34.0
1.00	0.10	0.60	45.6
1.00	0.10	0.80	54.5
1.00	0.10	1.00	65.1
1.00	0.40	0.00	55.8*

*Contained 0.001 mol dm⁻³ acrylonitrile.

obtained in nineteen different organic solvents. The solubility of reagents and reaction of PCC with primary and secondary alcohols limited the choice of solvents. There was no reaction with the chosen solvents. Kinetics was similar in all the solvents. The values of k_2 are recorded in Table 3.

Effect of temperature :

The rates of oxidation of the unsaturated acids were determined at different temperatures and the activation parameters were calculated (Table 2).

Solvent effect :

The rate constants, k_2 , in eighteen solvents (CS₂ was not considered, as the complete range of solvent parameters was not available) were correlated in terms of the linear solvation energy relationship [eq. (4)] of Kamlet *et al.*⁹,

$$\log k_2 = A_0 + p\pi^* + b\beta + a\alpha \quad (4)$$

In this equation, π^* represents the solvent polarity, β the hydrogen bond acceptor basicities and α is the hydrogen bond donor acidity. A_0 is the intercept term. It may be mentioned here that out of the 18 solvents, 12 have a value of zero for α . The results of correlation analyses in terms of eq. (4), a biparametric equation involving π^* and β , and separately with π^* and β are given below as eqs. (5)–(8),

$$\log k_2 = -3.34 + 1.30 (\pm 0.15)\pi^* + 0.12 (\pm 0.13)\beta - 0.05 (\pm 0.12)\alpha \quad (5)$$

$$R^2 = 0.8646; sd = 0.14; n = 18; \psi = 0.40$$

$$\log k_2 = -3.35 + 1.31 (\pm 0.14)\pi^* + 0.10 (\pm 0.11)\beta \quad (6)$$

$$R^2 = 0.8632; sd = 0.14; n = 18; \psi = 0.39$$

$$\log k_2 = -3.33 + 1.34 (\pm 0.14)\pi^* \quad (7)$$

$$r^2 = 0.8565; sd = 0.14; n = 18; \psi = 0.39$$

$$\log k_2 = -2.59 + 0.34 (\pm 0.28)\beta \quad (8)$$

$$r^2 = 0.0796; sd = 0.34; n = 18; \psi = 0.99$$

Here n is the number of data points and ψ the Exner's statistical parameter¹⁰.

Kamlet's⁹ triparametric equation explains *ca.* 86% of the effect of solvent on the oxidation. However, by Exner's criterion¹⁰ the correlation is not even satisfactory [cf. eq. (5)]. The major contribution is of solvent polarity. It alone accounted for *ca.* 85% of the data. Both β and α play relatively minor roles.

The data on the solvent effect were analysed in terms of Swain's equation¹¹ of cation- and anion-solvating concept of the solvents also, eq. (9),

$$\log k_2 = aA + bB + C \quad (9)$$

Here A represents the anion-solvating power of the solvent and B the cation-solvating power. C is the intercept term. ($A + B$) is postulated to represent the solvent polarity. The rates in different solvents were analysed in terms of eq. (9), separately with A and B and with ($A + B$).

$$\log k_2 = 0.59 (\pm 0.03) A + 1.33 (\pm 0.02) B - 3.51 \quad (10)$$

$$R^2 = 0.9961; sd = 0.02; n = 19; \psi = 0.08$$

$$\log k_2 = 0.39 (\pm 0.44) A - 2.60 \quad (11)$$

Table 2. Rate constants and activation parameters of the oxidation of unsaturated acids by PCC

Acids	$10^4 k_2/\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$				ΔH^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS^* (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	ΔG^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)
	288	298	308	318 K			
FA	6.42	11.3	19.1	33.8	39.4 ± 0.7	-170 ± 2	89.9 ± 0.5
CrA	19.8	34.2	60.3	104	39.7 ± 0.6	-159 ± 2	87.0 ± 0.5
MA	25.8	43.3	73.8	127	37.9 ± 0.8	-163 ± 2	86.4 ± 0.6
CiA	135	225	380	618	36.2 ± 0.4	-155 ± 1	82.4 ± 0.3

$$r^2 = 0.0455; sd = 0.36; n = 19; \psi = 1.01$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.29 (\pm 0.11) B - 3.32 \quad (12)$$

$$r^2 = 0.8977; sd = 0.12; n = 19; \psi = 0.28$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.09 \pm 0.10 (A + B) - 3.49 \quad (13)$$

$$r^2 = 0.8458; sd = 0.14; n = 19; \psi = 0.42$$

The rates of oxidation of cinnamic acid in different solvents showed an excellent correlation in Swain's equation [cf. eq. (9)] with the cation-solvating power playing the major role. In fact, the cation-solvation alone accounts for *ca.* 90% of the data. The correlation with the anion-solvating power was very poor. The solvent polarity, represented by $(A + B)$, also accounted for *ca.* 84% of the data. In view of the fact that solvent polarity is able to account for *ca.* 84% of the data, an attempt was made to correlate rate with the relative permittivity of the solvent. However, a plot of $\log k_2$ against the inverse of the relative permittivity is not linear ($r^2 = 0.5415$; $sd = 0.02$; $\psi = 0.73$).

Mechanism :

The observed acid-dependence of the reaction rate may be explained on the basis of a protonation of PCC in a pre-equilibrium [cf. eq. (14)], with both the protonated and deprotonated forms being active oxidizing species,

The reactions of alkenes with various Cr^{VI} derivatives have been widely studied. The most extensively studied derivative is chromyl chloride. The results of the present study are comparable with those obtained with chromyl chloride.

The low values of the enthalpies of activation indicate that bond-cleavage is not extensive in the formation of the activated complex. The formation of a rigid cyclic activated complex is indicated by the large negative values of the entropies of activation.

The probable structures if the activated complex are I, II, III and IV, III is a kin to the activated complexes of concerted *cis*-1,3-cycloaddition reactions, which are characterized by values of reaction constant close to zero¹². Therefore, an activated complex of type III is unlikely in view of the fact that the reactions of substituted styrenes¹³ and alkenes¹⁴ exhibit moderately large negative reaction constants (-1.99 and -2.63 , respectively).

In reactions involving fairly large degree of carbocationic character in the activated complex, reaction constant values of -3 to -5 have been observed¹⁵. In the oxidation of *trans*-monosubstituted cinnamic acid by acid borate. Reddy and Sundaram¹⁶ observed that electron-withdrawing groups have a little effect on the rate of oxidation while electron-

donating groups have substantial effect on the reactivity. They obtained a reaction constant of -3.7 for the electron-donating groups. The activated complex is proposed to be a benzylic carbocation in character. Therefore, the reported value of *ca.* -2 in the oxidation of styrenes¹³ by chromyl chloride mitigates against an activated complex with a fully developed positive charge (IV). In the present reaction also, replacement of a methyl group by a phenyl group results in a modest rate enhancement (*ca.* 7 times).

A perusal of the relative rates of the oxidation (cf. Table 3) showed that maleic acid is oxidized at a rate *ca.* 3 times that of fumaric acid. This militates against the formation of the activated complex. The formation of a four-member cyclic activated complex is likely to be more vulnerable to steric factors. Sterically the attack of PCC on the open face of maleic acid (having two hydrogens) is more facile than on fumaric acid. Had the activated complex been a four-membered cyclic structure, the difference in the rates of maleic and fumaric acids would have been much sharper. A formation of even the three-member cyclic activated complex (I) is less hindered in the oxidation of the *cis*-acid as compared to that in the *trans*-acid. However, the data against an involvement of the activated complex II is not conclusive. Freeman *et al.*^{5,13,14} also have not been able to show conclusively whether the activated complex had a three- or a four-member cyclic structure.

Table 3. Effect of solvents on the oxidation of cinnamic acid by PCC at 288 K

Solvents	$10^4 k_2$ ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$)	Solvents	$10^4 k_2$ ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$)
Chloroform	53.7	Acetic acid	16.2
1,2-Dichloroethane	60.3	Cyclohexane	4.07
Dichloromethane	56.2	Toluene	19.9
DMSO	135	Acetophenone	63.1
Acetone	50.1	THF	32.4
<i>N,N</i> -Dimethylformamide	87.1	<i>t</i> -Butyl alcohol	24.5
Butanone	39.8	1,4-Dioxane	30.2
Nitrobenzene	67.6	1,2-Dimethoxyethane	18.6
Benzene	21.4	Carbon disulphide	11.0
Ethyl acetate	23.4		

The analysis of the solvent effect also supports the proposed mechanism. The fact that the reaction proceeds faster in more polar solvents is in accordance with the formation of a partially charged activated complex from two neutral molecules. The relatively major contribution of the cation-solvating power of the solvents supports the generation of an electron-deficient carbon centre in the transition state.

Further, the relatively low magnitude of the regression coefficient, b , is consistent with the development of a partial positive charge in the activated complex. In the oxidation of benzaldehyde by pyridinium fluorochromate³, where the formation of a cabocationic activated complex has been postulated, the value of b is 1.73. To conclude, though both structures I and II are possible for the activated complex, the balance of evidence is in favour of I.

Experimental

Materials :

The unsaturated acids were commercial products and were used as supplied. PCC was prepared by the reported method¹ and its purity was ascertained by an iodometric method. Solvents were purified by the usual methods¹⁷. Due to non-aqueous nature of the medium, toluene-*p*-sulphonic acid (TsOH) was used as a source of hydrogen ions.

Product analysis :

Product analysis was carried out under kinetic conditions i.e. with an excess of the reductant over PCC. In a typical experiment, the unsaturated acid (0.2 mol) and PCC (6.18 g, 0.02 mol) were dissolved in 100 ml of DMSO and was allowed to stand for *ca.* 12 h to ensure completion of the reaction. The solution was then treated with an excess (200 cm³) of a saturated solution of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine in 2 mol dm⁻³ HCl and kept overnight in a refrigerator. The precipitated 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (DNP) was filtered off, dried, weighed, recrystallized from ethanol, and weighed again. The yields of DNP before and after recrystallization were 2.52 g (88%) and 2.26 g (79%), respectively. The DNP was found identical (m.p. and mixed m.p.) with the DNP of acetophenone, acetone and pyruvic acid in the oxidation of cinnamic, crotonic and maleic/fu-

maric acids, respectively. The oxidation state of chromium in completely reduced reaction mixtures, determined by an iodometric method, was 3.95 ± 0.06 .

Kinetic measurements :

The pseudo-first order conditions, were attained by keeping an excess ($\times 10$ or greater) of the reductant over PCC. The solvent was DMSO, unless specified otherwise. The reactions were followed at constant temperature (± 0.1 K) and by monitoring the decrease in the concentration of PCC spectrophotometrically at 356 nm for at least three half-lives. The pseudo-first order rate constant, k_{obs} , was evaluated from the linear ($r^2 > 0.995$) plots of $\log [\text{PCC}]$ against time. Duplicate kinetic runs indicated that the rate constants are reproducible to within $\pm 3\%$. The second order rate constant, k_2 , was evaluated from the relation : $k_2 = k_{\text{obs}}/[\text{reductant}]$. All experiments, other than those for studying the effect of hydrogen ions, were carried out in the absence of TsOH.

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